

Educational Attitude of the Bagri Community: A Socio-Educational Study

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Abstract

"Education is for all, not only for the ascribed and tall." Education is that part of our life that demands equality with equity. We cannot limit it within certain boundaries of our choice, as our constitution makes it a fundamental right. So, it is the foremost duty of each and every individual to take it to their advantage and make India a developed society, but still, education is a distant dream for some specific communities, like nomads, and one such community is the Bagri community/Gadiya Lohars. These are the artisans of Rajasthan, who are blacksmiths by profession. As part of society, Bagris also have the right to free and compulsory education in accordance with the RTE Act 2009, but still, they don't have access to education. This raised a question in the mind of the researcher. "Why so?" The present research was a qualitative study conducted to explore the attitude of parents towards the importance of education. The study aimed to understand the attitude of parents of the Bagri community towards the education of their children. A sample of 38 Bagri people, including 20 parents and 11 children from the areas of Dehradun and 7 parents from Pauri district, was selected for the study. The sample consisted of 10 male parents, 17 female parents, and 11 children. A self-made interview schedule was used for the study. The analysis was made by using a qualitative method.

Key word: Bagri Community, Attitude, Education, Denotified Community, Parents.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the right of every individual. According to the 86th Constitutional Amendment Act vide article 21A of the Indian Constitution, every child under the age of 6-14 years should have access to free and compulsory education, irrespective of caste, colour, creed, or any other background. The RTE Act 2009 seeks to give effect to this amendment, but still, education is not accessible to each section of society, especially the disadvantaged groups. Education is the only fundamental change agent in the process of the disadvantaged group's socio-economic development. One such group is the Bagri Community artisans. These are the most backwards and illiterate nomadic communities. They are blacksmiths by profession. They are also known as Gadiya Lohar. The history of their nomadism can be traced back to 1568 AD, when the Mughals conquered the Chittor fort and forced them, along with their king, Maharana Pratap, to leave the fort. Their ruler had gone into the forest for isolation and war preparation and was moving from place to place so that the enemies might not trace them. This required the settled blacksmiths also to live a nomadic life like their ruler, and since then they became nomads (Shashi, 2006). At the time of departure from Fort, Gadiya Lohar took vows that they would

not sleep on a cart, not light a lamp at night, not live in a house, etc., and conditioned that they would follow these vows until the kingdom and glory of Rana Pratap were restored, but this never happened, and they continue to follow the vows and live life like nomads. The level of education of the children of this community is very low; to earn a living, these communities often move from one place to another and therefore cannot send their children to school. Children are also actively involved in income-generating activities in this community (Raj, 2023).

There are several studies conducted on minority groups. Raj (2023) found that the lack of awareness among parents of slum children, poor social support from school teachers, and the necessity for earning a livelihood are the major factors responsible for the illiteracy of denotified tribes in Bhiwani, Haryana. Azad (2013) reported that the educational programs and development schemes have not helped improve the conditions of the tribals of Jammu and Kashmir. Similarly, Yadav & Sharma (2017) studied the health culture and health-seeking behaviour among the semi-nomadic Lohar Gadiyas of Malhotra town of Sagar District of Madhya Pradesh and found that health-seeking behaviour among them is highly influenced by the urban communities. It has been found in the literature that there is no Indian study that specifically focuses on the education of the Bagri community. This group received the least attention from the scholars, social workers, anthropologists, sociologists, and the government. The Bagri Lohar community had not received as much support from the government as they required. That is why the literacy among these people is minimal. Though the government had taken steps for their upliftment, like in 2016, when the government under the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment launched a skill development program for the girls of the Bagri community, no government scheme had come into action in connection with their education. The Bagris also want to become a part of society. They find themselves different and alone in the well-developed human settlements. Earlier, "Lohars were in huge demand, but after the technological advancement, the work of blacksmiths (Lohar) in India became obsolete due to the advancement of agricultural and household equipment. Nowadays, new cost-effective and modern tools are available in the market, which in turn leave Gadhiya/Bagri Lohars unemployed and are to lead a miserable life. The main causes behind their misery are illiteracy and non-acceptance by society. Their unique ethical lifestyle, which they don't want to lose at any cost, compels them to live aloof. Their rigid nature isolated them from human societies. But now, with the varied adversities of weather and the uncertainty of their trade, Bagris are in urgent need of a permanent habitat and awareness.

Education belongs to everyone, and in our country, it's a fundamental right too, but why are the children of the Bagri community not going to school and are playing all day? Do they not have to go to school? Why are they not accessing education? Why are their parents not sending them to school? What is the reason behind all this chaos? To find out the answers to all these questions, this topic has been selected.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study mainly focused on knowing the attitude of parents of the Bagri community towards the education of their children.

METHODOLOGY

This study is designed as a qualitative study; the interview method was used to provide an open platform for the stories of participants and to express their thoughts and opinions regarding education without limitations on options by using appropriate data-gathering tools. This

research includes the people of the Bagri Community living in the Dehradun and Pauri districts of Uttarakhand, having a population of 250 people. For the research, it was estimated that about 50 samples would be collected, but due to the non-cooperation of the people who were reluctant to face an interview, only 20 samples were collected through a purposive cluster sample. It was a great challenge to interview these people, as, according to them, they are the most excluded and neglected people in society, and due to the unwillingness of the government, they don't even have access to basic amenities like shelter, education, jobs, etc., which develops a sort of indifference for interaction. But after being convinced by the researcher, a few of them became ready for the interview.

For data collection, an interview schedule was prepared in which 7 questions were included. The interview schedule consisted of two sections. The questions of the first section were based on demographic information, and the second section was in connection with their education, reasons behind their illiteracy, hindrances in the way of accessing education for their children, and their aspirations for the future of their children. The data was collected from different settlements of the Bagri community of Dehradun and Srinagar (Pauri Garhwal). The researcher visited their settlements and took permission from them for the interview. Earlier, nobody was ready for the interview, as they had given a lot of interviews in the past with the hope of changing their lives, but nothing was done for them, and they were still facing small issues, like difficulties in making an Aadhar card, getting admissions in schools, permanent shelter, etc. After their counseling by the researchers, a few of them became ready to give an interview, and it started. First, the demographic information was gathered from the participants, and then questions were asked. The researcher assured the participants that their information would be kept confidential and used only for research purposes. As participants were illiterate, the interview questions were explained to them, and responses were recorded by the researcher in her handwriting, and she interpreted these responses for the research findings. After completing the interview, the researcher thanked them for their cooperation.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Attitude of the parents of the Bagri community towards the education of their children

Based on the interviews of the parents of the Bagri community, the following responses were found.

Statement 1: Have you ever gone to School? If yes, up to which level?

On this question, the answers given by the people of the Bagri community were "No," which shows that they were all illiterate. The reason behind this 100 % illiteracy might be poverty or their unawareness regarding education. In the words of one respondent

"Earlier, nobody sent children to school." (Respondent 2)

Statement 2: Whether your children go to school? If not, why?

Most of the Bagri parents replied "No" to this question when asked why. They quoted factors like "Difficulty in making Aadhar card, which renders them unable to get admission in school, lack of permanent settlement, and poverty" that prohibit them from accessing education. Few Bagris have children in the age group 4 to 5 years. When it was asked why they are not sending them to "Anganwadis". They replied that Anganwadi people don't allow the admission of their children, and if, anyhow, they get admission, within two to three days, they disqualify the admissions of their children, citing the reason that their children irritate and disturb others.

They also said that their children were deprived of the facilities provided to children in Anganwadis, like meals, rations, etc. The respondent's responses to this question are:

"You make our Aadhar card, we will send our children to School." (Respondent 3)

"If the government allots us a home to live in the very next day, we will send our children to school." (Respondent 5)

"Anganwadi people don't give admission to our children, and even if they do so, they refuse to accept them, quoting the reason that they irritate and disturb other children."

(Respondent 8)

Bagri people are homeless, Illiterate, and not aware of the importance of education in life. Moreover, if they want to enrol their children in Anganwadi or school, they are asked for an Aadhar card. They find it difficult to make an Aadhar card because they failed to produce permanent address proof. Even if they manage to get admission in Anganwadi due to the sort of discrimination mentioned above, the Bagri parents are not ready to send their children to school.

Statement 3: What are your expectations regarding your children's future?

Most of the Bagri parents replied that they want their children to get educated, have some respectable job, be treated equally with other people in the society, and should not be considered neglected and ignorant like them. To achieve these aims, they have to be educated. But they were very hopeless because of their struggle in meagre things like making Aadhar, getting admission in schools, Inequality among children, and discrimination in schools. Some of the respondents responded that:

"Our children should have a future and become property owners after getting educated".

(Respondent 9)

Statement 4: What is the main reason behind your illiteracy?

According to Bagri, they were socio-economically backwards and less exposed to the formal structure of education. They were economically weak and had to earn a living by working since childhood for their livelihood; therefore, they couldn't get schooling. Moreover, they didn't have any permanent settlement; therefore, due to frequent migration couldn't get education through a regular mode.

According to one of the respondents:

"Neither do we become educated nor do we become service class. Therefore, we can't get rid of our poverty". (Respondent 12)

Statement 5: If all the Bagri people present over here become educated, will things change? If yes, what could be the changes?

For this question, all Bagri parents replied "Yes" without any second thought. They said that literacy would eradicate their poverty and get them out of the awful situation.

Statement 6: What are your aspirations for your child's future?

For this question, most of the Bagri parents replied that they want their children to get educated, have some respectable job, be treated as other people in the society, and should not be considered neglected and ignorant like them. To achieve these aims, they have to be educated. But they were very hopeless because of their struggle in meagre things like making Aadhar, getting admission in schools, inequality among children, and discrimination in schools.

Statement 7: What are the main reasons for your being uneducated?

According to Bagri, they were socio-economically backwards and less exposed to the formal structure of education. They were economically weak and had to earn a living by working since childhood for their livelihood; therefore, they couldn't get schooling. Moreover, they didn't have any permanent settlement, even now they are forced to live on road roadside, under bridges, or under construction buildings where they have to pay rent to the contractors daily. They have to move from one place to another. Therefore, due to frequent migration couldn't get an education through a regular mode.

According to one of the respondents, they have to pay Rs 70 per day as rent to the flyover contractor. As they don't have a place to live, but beneath the flyovers. They believed that if they had been educated, they wouldn't have been fooled like this. Another respondent said that they have to beg for portable water from the people and use the railway track to defecate, or have to use paid shauchalayas. People with the least source of income have to pay for the aforesaid basic amenities. Is this justified? Earlier, we talked about equality and now equity, but these downtrodden masses are still far from being treated equally, and nobody bothers about this.

CONCLUSION

From this research, it is concluded that the Bagri people are 100 % illiterate. The reason behind this illiteracy might be poverty or their unawareness of education. Only a few of the Bagri children are school-going. Most of their children are not able to get admission in schools as they find it difficult to make an Aadhar card, which is the primary requirement for getting admission in school. They have no fixed placement; therefore, the Aadhar card is a herculean task for them. In the words of one of the respondents, "They are 'khanabadosh' people having no shelter. This study concluded that Bagris wanted to make their children respectable members of society. They also wanted to be on the other side of the road in well-structured houses rather than a shed or a torn tent house where they are living. There are lots of dreams in their mind for their children regarding education, Job, and money. They know that these dreams could be a reality only with one tool, which is education, but how to access it with their miserable situation is a big question. The research concluded that the prominent reason behind the illiteracy of parents of the Bagri community is poverty. To earn a bread and butter, they have to work since their childhood, therefore could not get a formal education. Moreover, their frequent forced movement from one place to another by the administration restricts their access to schools. People of the Bagri community have no permanent shelter, and most of the time they live either at the roadside or beneath the flyovers, for which they have to pay the contractors daily.

Researchers observed that they are the most forgotten people in society who need Government support very badly to move on from their pathetic situation. Nobody should be deprived of education. If this nomadic society is not able to access education, then the educational programmes of the government, like Universalisation of Elementary Education (UEE) and many others, will not be achieved for several years. The government should have a strict implementation programme regarding the education and development of these nomadic people (Bagris) who are poverty-stricken. The researcher observed that the eyes of each Bagri person were saying "*Kya aap humari stithi badal sakte ho*", which made the researcher speechless. The findings in this study have contributed to the understanding that the Bagri Community is facing a lot of difficulties in each and every aspect of life. They are just longing to fulfil their basic needs like "*Roti, Kapda aur Makaan*". Though they know the importance of education

still unable to access it. This study can help the Government in making new schemes, keeping in mind the disadvantaged and denotified communities like the Bagri, for their welfare. This study can help education policymakers keep an eye on the matter. Make educational policies pro Bagri children so that they can come forward and become a part of mainstream education, and so in life. Administrators can work on the present rigid admission process, and teachers should develop a feeling of acceptance, irrespective of the socio-economic background of the children. This study suggests that school administrators and teachers should have an attitude of inclusion for children belonging to different cultural backgrounds and disadvantaged groups so that everybody can access education. From time to time, awareness programs should be launched by teachers in different settlements of the disadvantaged communities based on education and its benefits. As we all know, the spirit of education lies in inclusion.

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